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Universally Diverging Grüneisen Ratio of Holographic Quantum Criticality

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E-mail: junkunzhao@itp.ac.cn; w.li@itp.ac.cn; liliphy@itp.ac.cn**Keywords:** Metallic quantum criticality, Grüneisen ratio, holographic duality**Abstract**

Quantum criticality is a hallmark of strongly correlated electron systems, as seen in heavy-fermion materials and high-temperature superconductors. Holographic duality provides a powerful framework to investigate these systems by translating them into weakly coupled classical gravity living in one higher dimension. Here, we exploit this approach to study a field-induced quantum critical point with dynamical exponent $z = 3$ in Einstein-Maxwell-Chern-Simons theory. Our analysis of its thermodynamic properties reveals a new universality class. Notably, we identify a diverging Grüneisen ratio Γ_B with universal scaling $\Gamma_B \sim T^{-2/3}$, a behavior that closely mirrors recent experiments on the heavy-fermion material CeRh_6Ge_4 . These findings advance our understanding of metallic quantum criticality and highlight the potential of holographic duality as a powerful tool for studying correlated quantum matters as well as their magnetocaloric applications.

1 Introduction

Quantum phase transitions (QPTs) occur at zero temperature in strongly correlated systems and are driven by the competition between quantum fluctuations and interactions [1, 2]. A continuous QPT features a quantum critical point (QCP) that separates different phases of matter. At the QCP, the system exhibits scale invariance and gives rise to nontrivial low-energy excitations that defy conventional quasiparticle descriptions. The influence of a QCP extends across a wide range of temperatures and tuning parameters, leading to universal scaling behavior in a region known as the quantum critical regime (QCR) [3, 4]. Over recent decades, quantum criticality has emerged as a central theme connecting condensed matter physics, quantum information, and quantum gravity, with significant theoretical and experimental progress [3–9].

Near the QCP, thermodynamics and response function exhibit universal quantum scaling laws due to the scale invariance of the system [2]. A prominent example is the Grüneisen ratio, $\Gamma_g \equiv 1/T (\partial T / \partial g)_S$, which characterizes the adiabatic temperature change per unit variation of external field g [10–13]. At the QCP, the Grüneisen ratio universally diverges as $\Gamma_g \propto T^{-1/z\nu}$ with z the dynamical critical exponent and ν the critical exponent of correlation length [14, 15]. In experiments, this Grüneisen ratio scaling of $T^{-1/z\nu}$ has been observed in quantum magnets [16, 17] and heavy-fermion materials [9, 18–24]. It thereby serves as a highly sensitive probe for detecting the QCP and determining its critical exponents [14, 15, 17, 24].

Recent studies on the heavy-fermion material CeRh_6Ge_4 reveal a diverging Grüneisen ratio $\Gamma_P \propto T^{-2/3}$ under external pressure P [9, 24], implying a novel QCP with cubic dispersion $z = 3$ and critical exponent $\nu = 1/2$. This continuous QPT goes beyond the Landau paradigm [24], and a theoretical understanding of the metallic QCP remains a formidable challenge. Nevertheless, the prevailing effective field theory framework for describing such metallic quantum criticality, developed by Hertz and Millis, is rooted in the conventional Landau paradigm [25, 26]. By integrating out the fermions to derive an effective action for the order parameter, this approach neglects the crucial backreaction of order parameter fluctuations on the fermionic degrees of freedom—a procedure that

Figure 1. Holographic description of quantum criticality. The dual quantum many-body system lives at the AdS boundary ($r = 0$) of the bulk gravity system. The holographic radial coordinate r encodes the energy scale or the renormalization group (RG) flow of the boundary system: processes near the boundary ($r \sim 0$) describe the short-distance, ultraviolet dynamics of the dual system, while processes in the interior ($r \gg 0$) capture its universal low-energy dynamics. Within this holographic framework, operators in the boundary quantum field theory are dual to classical fields in the bulk, where external sources for these operators are encoded in the asymptotic behavior of the corresponding bulk fields. QPTs are realized by tuning the asymptotic boundary conditions of the gravitational theory, which leads to distinct scaling geometries in the deep infrared regions. These far interior geometries capture the universal low-energy physics, which may be relativistic or non-relativistic in nature. The finite temperature physics of the boundary QPT, including its QCR, can be obtained by heating up the zero temperature scaling geometries, *i.e.* by considering a black hole located at $r = r_h$.

is dangerous [27]. Consequently, the specific universality class governing these quantum critical phenomena still requires further scrutiny. From a quantum field theory perspective, metallic QCPs involving both spin and charge degrees of freedom remains a long-standing problem for many-body calculations. Quantum Monte Carlo simulations suffer from the sign problem away from half-filling, while tensor network methods struggle to capture the highly entangled nature of such systems.

Here, employing holographic duality, we investigate the metallic QCP and gain new insights into its quantum scaling and universal behavior. Holography, or the Anti-de Sitter/Conformal Field Theory (AdS/CFT) correspondence, establishes a duality between a $(d+1)$ -dimensional gravitational theory and a d -dimensional quantum many-body system living on its boundary [28–30]. In the large N limit of AdS/CFT, the bulk dynamics is described by classical gravity coupled to matter fields. Holographic methods have proved successful in modeling strongly correlated systems without quasiparticle excitations, capturing not only conventional Fermi-liquid behavior but also exotic non-Fermi-liquid physics observed in strange metals [8, 31–33]. Notably, the emergent $\text{AdS}_2 \times \mathbb{R}^{d-1}$ near-horizon geometry in the $(d+1)$ extremal Reissner-Nördstorm-AdS black hole is responsible for the non-Fermi-liquid behavior in fermionic correlation functions [32], and admits a dimensional reduction to the two-dimensional Jackiw-Teitelboim gravity, revealing a low-energy duality to the Sachdev-Ye-Kitaev model [34–36]. Furthermore, holographic approaches provide a novel framework for realizing superconductivity or superfluidity [37–39], offer theoretical laboratories for exploring far-from-equilibrium dynamics [40–43], and reveal the intrinsic link between quantum information and gravity [44–46]. For comprehensive reviews, see *e.g.* Refs. [47–51].

A QPT is holographically described as follows: by continuously tuning a non-thermal parameter, the system evolves from an ultraviolet fixed point toward distinct infrared fixed points—realized as different scaling geometries, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Notable examples of holographic QPTs include Berezinskii-Kosterlitz-Thouless [52, 53], cohesive-fractionalized [54, 55], metal-insulator [56], and Weyl Semimetal transitions [57–59], etc. Of particular interest is the five-dimensional Einstein-Maxwell-Chern-Simons (EMCS) theory [60–64], which is simple and universal in the sense that it only contains metric and gauge fields yet can give rise to novel magnetic field-induced QPT [65–67]. One appealing property of this model is that it hosts a $z = 3$ QCP, offering a unique theoretical platform to investigate this notable class of quantum criticality observed in heavy-fermion materials such as CeRh_6Ge_4 [9, 24]. In this work, we investigate the field-induced QCP and quantum criticality in the five-dimensional EMCS theory, aiming to offer a new perspective for understanding analogous behavior in the metallic QCP of heavy-fermion materials. Although quantum criticality has been

Figure 2. Entropy density s and its quantum critical behavior. **a** Contour plot of the entropy density in T - B plane. White lines represent the isentropic lines, while the red dot represents the QCP. **b** Temperature-dependent power m of entropy $S \propto T^m$, where $m = \frac{d \log s}{d \log T}$. Orange region indicates the QCR hosting the quantum critical scaling $s \propto T^{1/3}$. Blue region represents the fractionalized phase, while the purple region is the cohesive phase. **c** Temperature dependence of entropy in different fields. Inset illustrates the zero point entropy at the fractionalized phase. **d** Quantum critical scaling function $\phi_s(x)$ extracted from the collapse of entropy density data for temperatures $10^{-6} \leq T \leq 10^{-4}$. The plots are shown for $k = k_{\text{susy}} = 2/\sqrt{3}$ and $\mu = 1$.

extensively studied within the holographic framework, to the best of our knowledge, a systematic investigation of the universality class and critical behavior—particularly the Grüneisen ratio—remains absent, despite their being hallmark characteristics of quantum criticality and magnetocaloric scaling near QCP.

2 Holographic quantum critical point

We consider the simple holographic model exhibiting magnetic field-induced QPTs, with the action given by

$$S = \frac{1}{16\pi G_N} \int d^5x \sqrt{-g} \left(R + \frac{12}{L^2} - \frac{1}{4} F_{ab} F^{ab} + \frac{k}{24} \epsilon^{abcde} A_a F_{bc} F_{de} \right), \quad (1)$$

where G_N is the Newton's constant, L denotes the AdS radius, and k is the Chern-Simons coupling. The gauge field strength is defined as $F_{ab} = \partial_a A_b - \partial_b A_a$. For $k = 2/\sqrt{3}$, the action (1) corresponds to the bosonic sector of five-dimensional minimal supergravity and is a consistent truncation of Type IIB supergravity or M-theory [68, 69]. From a bottom-up perspective, the parameter k can be treated as free. In our construction, the bulk theory is relativistic and admits asymptotically AdS black hole solutions, in contrast to non-relativistic holography [70–72]. The $z = 3$ scaling is not built into the asymptotic geometry, but instead emerges from the near-horizon infrared dynamics of the system. Without loss of generality, we will set $16\pi G_N = L = 1$.

The quantum many-body system via the holographic approach resides in three-dimensional space \mathbb{R}^3 with coordinates (x_1, x_2, x_3) , and features both a finite charge density and a magnetic field B aligned with the x_3 -axis. The magnetic field-driven QPT is holographically realized through transition between distinct infrared scaling geometries: a fractionalized phase characterized by a charged $\text{AdS}_2 \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^2$ horizon for $B < B_c$, and a cohesive phase with a neutral $\text{AdS}_3 \times \mathbb{R}^2$ horizon for $B > B_c$ [67, 73]. Similar fractionalization transitions have also been identified in other holographic models of QPTs [54, 56]. A notable property of this holographic framework is that $z = 3$ emerges intrinsically from the underlying gravitational dynamics, in contrast to the Hertz-Millis approach where $z = 3$ is derived from a one-loop approximation (see Appendix A) [14, 25, 26]. The quantum critical behavior, particularly the dynamical critical exponent z , is governed by the Chern-Simons

Figure 3. Specific heat near the QCP. a Isothermal specific heat as a function of magnetic field. The vertical dashed line marks the critical field $B_c \approx 0.332$ of the QCP. **b** Scaling function $\phi_c(x)$ of the specific heat.

coupling k : it follows $z = k/(1 - k)$ for $1/2 < k \leq 3/4$, and continuously transitions to $z = 3$ for $k > 3/4$ [65, 66]. However, despite being proposed some time ago, its thermodynamic properties—including the specific heat, magnetization, and susceptibility—remain poorly understood, and its universality class and magnetocaloric effect (MCE) have yet to be investigated. A systematic study of these aspects is thus crucial for unlocking the full potential of this framework in describing strongly correlated systems.

Here, we focus on the $k = 2/\sqrt{3}$ supersymmetric case, corresponding to a $z = 3$ QCP. We work in the grand canonical ensemble, where the free energy density depends on temperature T , chemical potential μ , and magnetic field B . The equilibrium properties associated with the QPT are obtained straightforwardly using the holographic dictionary after solving the bulk equations of motion numerically. See Appendices B and C for more details. Owing to the scale invariance of the system, all physical quantities are normalized by the chemical potential μ , *i.e.* we set $\mu = 1$.

In Fig. 2a, we show a contour plot of entropy density s in the T - B plane. The QCR can be identified by the power of entropy, as shown in Fig. 2b. Within a well-defined cone-like region, the entropy exhibits quantum critical scaling governed by the exponent d/z , where d represents the effective spatial dimension of the QPT. Unlike the conventional quantum critical system, in which the isentropic lines reach their minimum in the QCR, the temperature decreases monotonically with B during an adiabatic demagnetization process. Notably, this cooling effect has significant implications for the Grüneisen ratio, as will be discussed in Sec. 4. Fig. 2c displays the temperature dependence of s for various fields. At high temperatures, these entropy curves in different fields overlap, following the same trivial T^3 scaling. In the cohesive phase ($B > B_c$), the low-temperature entropy crosses over to a $s \propto T$ scaling, which describes the excitation of a chiral fermion propagating along the direction of the magnetic field (x_3 -axis) [67]. Above the QCP at $B = B_c$, the low-temperature entropy exhibits a quantum critical behavior $s \propto T^{d/z} \propto T^{1/3}$. In the fractionalized phase ($B < B_c$), there exists a zero point entropy at the ground state, where the system hosts macroscopic degeneracy. A more detailed discussion of the residual entropy in the $B < B_c$ region is provided in Appendix D.

Near the QCP, the singular part of the thermal entropy exhibits a universal behavior $s = T^{d/z} \phi_s(x)$ with $d/z = 1/3$, which is obtained by the semi-analytical matching method [65, 66]. Here, $\phi_s(x)$ is the universal scaling function with $x \equiv (B - B_c)/T^{2/3}$. At the QCP, the magnetic field effectively freezes the x_1 and x_2 directions in the near-horizon geometry, such that the resulting geometry corresponds precisely to the three-dimensional part of the ‘‘Schrödinger’’ spacetime [66, 74, 75], indicating that the low-energy dynamics of the dual theory is reduced to an effective $1 + 1$ system with the spatial dimension $d = 1$. Applying the standard scaling ansatz, $s \sim T^{d/z} \phi_s((B - B_c)T^{-1/z\nu})$, yields $z = 3$ and $z\nu = 3/2$, which implies $\nu = 1/2$. As shown in Fig. 2d, the universal quantum critical scaling function $\phi_s(x)$ is obtained from the data collapse of entropy density. Remarkably, we note that a $z = 3$ QCP, corresponding to a cubic dispersion relation $\omega \sim k^3$, has also been observed recently in some heavy-fermion systems [9, 21, 24].

Furthermore, the specific heat $c = T(\partial s/\partial T)_{B,\mu}$ also exhibits universal behavior near the QCP. Fig. 3a illustrates the isothermal specific heat as a function of the magnetic field. As the temperature decreases, the specific heat density exhibits a pronounced peak in the vicinity of the critical field (vertical dashed line). As shown in Fig. 3b, the specific heat exhibits accurate data collapse onto a universal scaling function $\phi_c(x)$ near the QCR, thereby validating the critical exponents z, ν derived from entropy scaling (see Fig. 2c-d). Different from the conventional scaling function with double peaks [76], the sharp peaks in Fig. 3a collapse onto a single peak in Fig. 3b. This single peak may

Figure 4. Magnetic properties of the QPT. **a** Magnetic field dependence of magnetization M_B at different temperatures. The vertical dashed line marks the location of QCP. **b** Behavior of magnetic susceptibility χ_B with respect to B for various temperatures. The plots are shown for $k = k_{\text{susy}} = 2/\sqrt{3}$ and $\mu = 1$.

therefore be regarded as a feature of the specific heat scaling function ϕ_c in the present holographic model. A similar single peak structure also appears for the $z = 2$ QCP shown in Fig. 10b, suggesting a possible general pattern. Thus, only the right peak of c reliably identifies the boundary of the QCR $B - B_c \propto T^{1/z\nu}$, while the left boundary cannot be determined from the specific heat. We also attempted to identify the left QCR boundary using other physical quantities, yet no suitable quantity was found.

3 Magnetization, order parameter and universality class of the QCP

The magnetization $M_B = -(\partial w/\partial B)_{T,\mu}$, derived from the free energy density w , is shown in Fig. 4a as a function of the magnetic field B at different temperatures. For each curve, M_B exhibits a non-monotonic behavior: it increases from zero field, reaches a maximum at an intermediate value of B , and then decreases upon the increasing of B . While the magnetization varies smoothly at high temperatures, its derivative becomes discontinuous at low temperatures, signaling a cusp singularity across the QPT (see Fig. 4a). From the maximum of M_B at each temperature T_0 , located at B_0 in Fig. 4a, we find that they obey the scaling relation $B_0 - B_c \propto T_0^{0.69}$. The extracted exponent 0.69 is close to the expected value $1/z\nu = 2/3$ for quantum critical crossovers. This suggests that M_B , like the specific heat, may be used to identify the right boundary of the QCR. Notably, since no symmetry change is associated with this QPT, it was proposed in [65] that this is a metamagnetic QPT, which is empirically characterized by a rapid increase in magnetization toward a critical field, followed by saturation at large fields [77]. In contrast, our explicit calculations reveal no such rapid magnetization increase; instead, a cusp singularity emerges near the QCP (see Fig. 4a), indicating a departure from the conventional picture of metamagnetic QPT [77].

Fig. 4b displays the magnetic susceptibility $\chi_B = (\partial M_B/\partial B)_{T,\mu}$ as a function of B . At high temperatures, χ_B decreases monotonically from a positive value to a negative value with the increasing of B . At low temperatures, it first increases to a maximum before reaching B_c , then decreases to a minimum after passing B_c , and finally increases again with further increase in B . Note that the non-monotonic behavior of χ_B (see *e.g.* the yellow curve in Fig. 4b) reflects the rapid variation of M_B near the QCP. In particular, χ_B becomes discontinuous in the zero temperature limit. Near the QCP, the magnetic susceptibility obeys the scaling form $\chi_B \propto T^{-\alpha/z\nu}$ with α the specific-heat exponent [78]. As shown in Fig. 4b, χ_B remains finite as $T \rightarrow 0$, indicating $\alpha = 0$. The distinct behavior of both M_B and χ_B leads us to conclude that the dual strongly coupled quantum many-body system undergoes a second order QPT from a paramagnetic phase ($\chi_B > 0$) for $B < B_c$ to a diamagnetic phase ($\chi_B < 0$) for $B > B_c$. Approaching the QCP, the magnetization varies linearly with the magnetic field, while the susceptibility remains approximately constant.

Previously, the critical exponents z and ν for the QPT have been extracted from the scaling behavior of the entropy density, with their validity further corroborated by the data collapse of both the entropy and the specific heat. We determined α from the magnetic susceptibility. Importantly, these exponents satisfy the quantum hyperscaling relation $2 - \alpha = \nu(d + z)$ with effective spatial dimension $d = 1$, confirming the standard scaling scenario. A complete characterization of the QCP usually requires determining the full set of critical exponents. However, the QPT considered here goes beyond the conventional Landau-Ginzburg paradigm, as it occurs without any symmetry breaking. Thus, there is no natural local order parameter dictated by symmetry. In such cases, suitable order parameters are often defined as the zero-temperature limit of quantities that are finite

Figure 5. Order parameters of the holographic QCP. **a** Magnetic field dependence of the ratio of parallel shear viscosity to entropy density η/s at an extremely low temperature $T = 5 \times 10^{-7}$. The dashed gray line denotes a linear fit near the QCP. The inset provides an enlarged view of η/s in the vicinity of the QCP. **b** Magnetic field dependence of the ratio of fractionalized charge to total charge ρ_{frac}/ρ at an extremely low temperature $T = 5 \times 10^{-7}$. The dashed gray line denotes a linear fit near the QCP. The inset shows an enlarged view of ρ_{frac}/ρ in the vicinity of the QCP. The plots are shown for $k = k_{\text{susy}} = 2/\sqrt{3}$ and $\mu = 1$.

in one phase, vanish in the other, and exhibit well-defined critical behavior near the QCP. Here, we identify two physical quantities that serve as suitable order parameters: the ratio of parallel shear viscosity to entropy density η/s [73], and the ratio of fractionalized charge to total charge, ρ_{frac}/ρ . Although η/s is a transport coefficient, it can clearly distinguish the two phases and therefore serves as a useful diagnostic of QPTs beyond the Landau paradigm. The fractionalized charge ρ_{frac} denotes the contribution to the electric flux originating from the charged black hole horizon. Particularly, the emergence of charge fractionalization may hold the key to understanding the Fermi surface reconstruction that accompanies a second order QPT. As shown in Fig. 5, both η/s and ρ_{frac}/ρ are finite for $B < B_c$, decrease linearly with B near the QCP, and vanish identically for $B > B_c$.

In the conventional Landau framework, the order parameter vanishes near the QCP as $\sim |B - B_c|^\beta$, where β is the order parameter exponent. By analogy, the order parameters defined above imply a critical exponent $\beta^* = 1$. Here the asterisk is used to distinguish this exponent from the conventional β in the Landau paradigm. Using the scaling relations among critical exponents [2, 79], we further obtain the remaining exponents, including the susceptibility exponent γ^* , the critical isotherm exponent δ^* , and the anomalous dimension η^* . Consequently, the complete set of critical exponents is summarized in Table 1. To the best of our knowledge, this set of critical exponents does not correspond to any previously known universality class. To investigate whether the properties of this $z = 3$ QCP are generic, we also examine the case $k = 3/2$, which yields the same dynamical critical exponent. We find that the universal entropy scaling function $\phi_s(x)$ takes the same form for different values of k (see Appendix D), implying the same singular part of the free energy and hence the same quantum universality class. Therefore, other observables derived from the free energy exhibit the same universal behavior near the QCP, while the full set of critical exponents remains unchanged. This provides further evidence for the robustness of the novel $z = 3$ universality class identified in our work. Given that this universality class with $z = 3$ is derived from the holographic framework involving a charged black hole with Chern-Simons interactions, we designate it the ‘‘EMCS cubic universality class.’’

Critical exponent	α	β^*	γ^*	δ^*	η^*	ν	z	d
EMCS theory	0	1	0	1	2	$\frac{1}{2}$	3	1

Table 1. Critical exponents of the EMCS cubic universality class. The asterisk denotes the critical exponents with the order parameter η/s or ρ_{frac}/ρ , which is different from the critical exponents of the traditional Landau phase transition with symmetry breaking. The last column $d = 1$ denotes the effective spatial dimension of the QCP.

4 Universally diverging Grüneisen ratio

Here, we explore a novel phenomenon, magnetocalorics of the holographic QCP. Magnetic Grüneisen ratio is defined as $\Gamma_B = \frac{1}{T} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial B} \right)_{s,\mu} = - \frac{(\partial s / \partial B)_{T,\mu}}{T(\partial s / \partial T)_{B,\mu}}$, measuring the adiabatic temperature response to an infinitesimal change in the external field. Near a field-induced QCP, the Grüneisen ratio generally exhibits a universal divergence, with $\Gamma_B \sim T^{-1/z\nu}$ at the critical field, serving both as a sensitive probe of quantum criticality and as a measure of the enhanced magnetic cooling [14]. Fig. 6a shows

Figure 6. Universally diverging Grüneisen ratio near the QCP. **a** Magnetic Grüneisen ratio Γ_B as a function of magnetic field B . Inset illustrates the Grüneisen ratio near the QCP. **b** Scaling function $\phi_\Gamma(x)$ of Grüneisen ratio near the QCP. The inset shows the temperature-dependent scaling of Γ_B at $B = B_c$. The plots are shown for $k = k_{\text{susy}} = 2/\sqrt{3}$ and $\mu = 1$.

the magnetic Grüneisen ratio Γ_B as a function of magnetic field B for various temperatures. At high temperatures, Γ_B initially increases with the magnetic field, forming a peak before reaching B_c , and then decreases monotonically. This peak grows and ultimately diverges as the temperature is lowered. Notably, the sign of Γ_B remains positive across all magnetic fields, which is consistent with the monotonic increase of temperature with B along each isentropic curve, as shown in Fig. 2a.

In particular, Γ_B displays only a single peak across the QCP, in sharp contrast with the conventional peak-dip structure and sign reversal in Grüneisen ratio seen in most QPTs [15]. It is empirically observed — and confirmed in many models — that the entropy is maximal at the QCP, meaning it decreases more slowly with temperature along $B = B_c$ (or $x = 0$) than in other phases. Theoretically, however, there could exist quantum phases in which s decreases even more slowly than that along $B = B_c$. In such a case, the isentropes would vary monotonically with the external field, and the Grüneisen ratio would exhibit no sign change. Interestingly, our model indeed realizes a concrete example of this type, exhibiting no sign reversal in the Grüneisen ratio Γ_B . Notably, similar phenomena in Γ_P were identified in the 3D XY model of pressure induced QPT in recent studies [80]. For practical implementations such as magnetic refrigeration, the absence of a sign reversal in the Grüneisen parameter Γ_B provides a significant advantage: the cooling procedure is not constrained by the need to operate either above or below the critical magnetic field.

To better understand the quantum critical MCE in this model, we perform a scaling analysis of the diverging Grüneisen ratio Γ_B . As shown in Fig. 6b, we show the data collapse of Γ_B near the QCP. The $\Gamma_B(B - B_c)$, when plotted against x , collapse onto universal curves, confirming the quantum critical scaling of the Grüneisen ratio. In the insert of Fig. 6b, we plot the temperature dependence of Γ_B above the QCP ($B = B_c$ or $x = 0$). Above the QCP, the numerical results follow the scaling $\Gamma_B \propto T^{-1/z\nu} = T^{-2/3}$, demonstrating the universally diverging of Grüneisen ratio [14]. On either side of $B = B_c$, the $T^{-2/3}$ scaling only persists in an intermediate temperature range and breaks down as the system passes through the QCR at extremely low temperatures. Derived from critical scaling of the entropy density $s = T^{1/3}\phi_s(x)$, the Grüneisen ratio in the QCR should satisfy a scaling form of $\Gamma_B = T^{-2/3}\phi_\Gamma(x)$, where $\phi_\Gamma(x)$ is the universal scaling function of Γ_B .

5 Discussions

Our work provides a novel approach for metallic quantum criticality in strongly correlated systems such as heavy-fermion materials, offering new insights into field-induced QPTs and charting promising directions for future research. Specifically, we have discovered the “EMCS cubic universality class” for the first time and investigated the associated MCE in strongly coupled systems hosting a magnetic field-driven QCP, described holographically by a five-dimensional EMCS theory. Understanding the metallic QCP has been a long-term challenge for many-body approaches, especially for unconventional QCPs that fall outside the Landau-Ginzburg paradigm. The presence of quantum criticality is demonstrated through the scaling behavior of the entropy and the specific heat, as shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively. The magnetic properties of the system are studied in Fig. 4. An interesting finding is the emergence of a cusp singularity in the magnetization M_B across the transition—a feature distinct from conventional metamagnetic QPTs. The behavior of magnetic susceptibility χ_B further indicates a continuous second order QPT from a paramagnetic state to a diamagnetic phase. As shown in Fig. 5, the order parameters of the QPT are identified as the ratio of parallel shear viscosity to entropy density η/s , and the ratio of fractionalized charge to total charge

ρ_{frac}/ρ .

Moreover, we introduce the Grüneisen ratio Γ_B —a standard and sensitive probe of quantum criticality in condensed matter physics—into black hole physics and holography, establishing a direct bridge between bulk gravitational solutions and experimentally measurable observables in boundary quantum systems. Our work provides the first demonstration of the universal divergence of Γ_B near a holographic QCP. Notably, in our system Γ_B exhibits neither the sign reversal nor the peak-dip structure commonly observed in many quantum critical systems (see Fig. 6). Above the QCP, we reveal the quantum critical scaling $\Gamma_B \propto T^{-1/z\nu} \propto T^{-2/3}$ with $z = 3$ and $\nu = 1/2$. These results confirm the utility of the magnetic Grüneisen ratio as a precise tool for locating the QCP and determining critical exponents in strongly correlated holographic quantum matter. Given that critical behaviors are largely insensitive to the microscopic details of the theory, the holographic approach proves to be a powerful tool for uncovering different universality classes and scaling functions.

We have demonstrated that a remarkably simple holographic model can capture rich quantum critical behaviors reminiscent of heavy-fermion materials. The holographic construction naturally yields a class of $z = 3$ QCPs, which bears a promising connection to the cubic dispersion relation recently observed in certain heavy-fermion compound CeRh_6Ge_4 [24]. Our model predicts a universally diverging Grüneisen ratio, $\Gamma_B \sim T^{-2/3}$, near the QCP, consistent with recent experimental observations. The diverging Γ_B indicates the universally enhanced magnetic cooling near the QCP [14, 15], which is a valuable resource for ultralow-temperature refrigeration with quantum materials [12, 13, 81, 82].

In addition to the $z = 3$ QCP discussed above, our model is capable of realizing other dynamical exponents. As a demonstration, we present in Appendix E a $z = 2$ QCP exhibiting a third order QPT. Due to its third order nature, a complete set of critical exponents cannot be determined via the standard relations between critical exponents [2, 79]. Nevertheless, we find that the Grüneisen ratio still diverges, and provides an effective way to extract $z\nu$. Remarkably, the value of $z\nu$ obtained from Γ_B is consistent with that deduced from the data collapse of the entropy and specific heat. This remarkable consistency suggests that the universal scaling laws governing the divergence of the Grüneisen ratio, established for second order QPTs, could be extended to third-order transitions.

A natural extension, incorporating additional degrees of freedom, would enable the model to capture other experimentally relevant phenomena like electrical conductivity, paving the way toward a holographic description of strange metal behavior consistent with observations. It would also be important to compute the fermion spectral function following [8, 31, 32], thereby enabling direct access to collective excitations near this QCP. The fractionalization picture described here may be an important element for understanding the large-to-small Fermi surface transition, shedding new light on the origin of strange metallicity in heavy-fermion materials [54, 83]. Although our model features a finite $z = 3$ QCP, distinct from the widely studied $z = \infty$ local quantum criticality associated with the near horizon AdS_2 geometry, it would be interesting to develop a qualitative understanding of our results within the framework of semi-holography [84–86]. In the present model, numerical evidence points to a finite entropy density in the ground state of the fractionalized phase. To circumvent this issue and better model realistic quantum critical systems, future work could focus on setups that exhibit vanishing ground state entropy in both phases. One promising route is to introduce helical order, which supports a spatially modulated phase spanning the QCP [87, 88]. Such a configuration may be viewed as a holographic realization of a chiral magnetic spiral [89] and could be closely related to nematic phases observed in metamagnetic materials [90]. It would be interesting to investigate finite N effects on the QPT studied in this work and to examine whether such corrections modify its critical properties.

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A Hertz-Millis theory

Here, we present a brief introduction of Hertz-Millis theory and discuss key similarities and differences with our holographic model. The Hertz-Millis theory of quantum criticality provides a standard framework for describing magnetic field-induced QPTs [25, 26]. In this approach, the fermionic degrees of freedom are integrated out, yielding an effective bosonic theory for the order parameter ϕ that can then be studied using renormalization group methods. The effective action in d spatial

dimensions takes the form

$$S_{\text{HM}} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}, i\omega_n} \left(\delta + \mathbf{k}^2 + \frac{|\omega_n|}{\Gamma_k} \right) |\phi_{\mathbf{k}, i\omega_n}|^2 + u \int_0^{1/T} d\tau \int d^d \mathbf{r} \phi(\mathbf{r}, \tau)^4, \quad (2)$$

where $\Gamma_k = \Gamma_0 \mathbf{k}^{z-2}$ is the Landau damping rate, and δ and u are parameters inherited from the underlying electron Hamiltonian. In particular, δ serves as the tuning parameter that changes sign as one varies some control parameter in the microscopic model, while u denotes the strength of the interaction, which is assumed to depend negligibly on Hamiltonian parameters over the range of interest. The sum runs over bosonic Matsubara frequencies ω_n and wave vectors \mathbf{k} . Here, the scalar field ϕ represents the order parameter of the QPT. The case $z = 2$ describes an antiferromagnetic spin-density-wave transition in a metal, whereas $z = 3$ may apply to the critical endpoint of a metamagnetic first-order transition in $d = 2, 3$. This approach, however, relies on the assumption that the fermionic degrees of freedom can be safely integrated out—a procedure that is justified only when they are treated as high energy modes [27, 91].

In $d = 1$, the Hertz-Millis action is invariant under the scaling transformation $\omega \rightarrow \lambda^3 \omega$, $\mathbf{k} \rightarrow \lambda \mathbf{k}$ at the QCP if $z = 3$. Moreover, choosing $\delta = B - B_c$ as the tuning parameter, we find that it has the same scaling dimension as momentum squared, $[B - B_c] = [\mathbf{k}^2] = 2$, and therefore acts as a relevant coupling in the theory. These properties are consistent with the scaling behavior $s \propto T^{1/3}$ for Chern Simons coupling $k > 3/4$. Nevertheless, the holographic model and the Hertz-Millis theory represent fundamentally different frameworks for quantum criticality. The Hertz-Millis theory is an effective field theory formulated in terms of an order parameter, whereas the present holographic model does not possess a natural local order parameter of this type. The holographic construction therefore provides an alternative route to quantum criticality in strongly coupled quantum matter and may capture some essential physics beyond the conventional paradigm.

B Equations of motion and holographic renormalization

The equations of motion derived from the EMCS action (1) are given by

$$R_{ab} - \frac{1}{2} g_{ab} (R + 12) - \frac{1}{2} \left(F_{ac} F_b{}^c - \frac{1}{4} g_{ab} F_{cd} F^{cd} \right) = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla_b F^{ba} + \frac{k}{8} \epsilon^{abcde} F_{bc} F_{de} = 0.$$

The dual magnetic field-induced QPT is described by the following dyonic black hole [66, 73]

$$ds^2 = \frac{1}{r^2} \left[- (f - h^2 p^2) dt^2 + 2ph^2 dt dx_3 + g(dx_1^2 + dx_2^2) + h^2 dx_3^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f} \right], \quad (4)$$

$$A = A_t dt - \frac{B}{2} x_2 dx_1 + \frac{B}{2} x_1 dx_2 - A_z dx_3,$$

where f, g, h, p, A_t , and A_z are functions of radial coordinate r which is identified as the energy scale of the dual boundary theory. In these coordinates, the asymptotically AdS boundary lies at $r = 0$, and the black hole event horizon is located at $r = r_h$, where all bulk fields are regular with $f(r_h) = 0$ (See Fig. 1). The constant $B = F_{x_1 x_2}$ denotes the background magnetic field, which is aligned along the x_3 direction.

Inserting the ansatz (4) into the above field equations (3) yields a set of six coupled second order differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{gh}{r} (A'_t + pA'_z) \right]' + kBA'_z &= 0, \\ \left[\frac{g}{rh} (ph^2 A'_t - (f - h^2 p^2) A'_z) \right]' - kBA'_t &= 0, \\ \frac{f''}{f} + \frac{h''}{h} + \left(\frac{f'}{f} - \frac{g'}{g} \right) \left(\frac{h'}{h} - \frac{3}{r} \right) - \frac{g'^2}{2g^2} - \frac{h^2 p'^2}{f} + \frac{r^2 A_z'^2}{2h^2} - \frac{B^2 r^2}{fg^2} - \frac{r^2 (A'_t + pA'_z)^2}{f} &= 0, \\ \frac{g''}{g} + \frac{g'}{3g} \left(\frac{f'}{f} - \frac{g'}{g} - \frac{h'}{h} - \frac{3}{r} \right) + \frac{2h'}{h} \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{f'}{3f} \right) + \frac{B^2 r^2}{3fg^2} - \frac{h^2 p'^2}{3f} &= 0, \\ \frac{h''}{h} + \left(\frac{h'}{h} - \frac{g'}{2g} \right) \left(\frac{2f'}{3f} + \frac{g'}{3g} - \frac{2}{r} \right) + \frac{h^2 p'^2}{3f} + \frac{r^2 A_z'^2}{2h^2} - \frac{B^2 r^2}{3fg^2} &= 0, \\ p'' + \left(\frac{g'}{g} + \frac{3h'}{h} - \frac{3}{r} \right) p' - \frac{r^2 A'_t A'_z}{ph^2} - \frac{r^2 A_z'^2}{h^2} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the prime represents the derivative with respect to r . Additionally, the following constraint equation:

$$\left(\frac{g'}{g} + \frac{f'}{2f}\right) \left(\frac{g'}{g} + \frac{h'}{h} - \frac{3}{r}\right) - \frac{3g'^2}{4g^2} - \frac{3h'}{rh} + \frac{6(f-1)}{r^2f} + \frac{Br^2}{4fg^2} - \frac{r^2A_z'^2}{4h^2} + \frac{h^2p'^2}{4f} + \frac{r^2(A_t + pA_z')^2}{4f} = 0, \quad (6)$$

is automatically satisfied when the above equations hold. Denoting the constraint equation (6) as $\text{CON}(r) = 0$, we use it as a check of numerical accuracy, as demonstrated in Appendix C.

The asymptotic expansions of the bulk fields near the AdS boundary $r \rightarrow 0$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} f(r) &= 1 + \frac{B^2}{6}r^4 \ln r + f_4r^4 + \dots, & g(r) &= 1 - \frac{B^2}{12}r^4 \ln r - h_4r^4 + \dots, \\ h(r) &= 1 + \frac{B^2}{12}r^4 \ln r + h_4r^4 + \dots, & p(r) &= p_4r^4 + \dots, \\ A_t(r) &= \mu + A_{t2}r^2 + \dots, & A_z(r) &= A_{z2}r^2 + \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where the reparameterization freedom $r \rightarrow r + \xi$ in the radial direction has been fixed by setting $f'(r)|_{r=0} = 0$. Note that the above expansions contain logarithmic terms, which commonly arise in holographic renormalization. In the present setup, these terms are closely associated with the trace anomaly of the four dimensional boundary theory induced by the background magnetic field. Near the black hole horizon $r = r_h$, the bulk fields are regular and can be expanded as

$$\begin{aligned} f(r) &= (r_h - r)f_0 + \dots, & g(r) &= g_0 + \dots, & h(r) &= h_0 + \dots, \\ p(r) &= (r_h - r)p_0 + \dots, & A_t(r) &= (r_h - r)A_{t0} + \dots, & A_z(r) &= A_{z0} + \dots. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Note that, the full bulk solutions for non-vanishing magnetic field are only accessible numerically. We therefore discretize the background equations of motion using a pseudo-spectral method [92] and solve the resulting nonlinear algebraic system by Newton-Raphson iteration, imposing appropriate asymptotic boundary conditions and horizon regularity conditions. A useful scaling symmetry

$$(t, x_1, x_2, x_3, r) \rightarrow y(t, x_1, x_2, x_3, r), \quad (A_t, A_z) \rightarrow \left(\frac{A_t}{y}, \frac{A_z}{y}\right), \quad B \rightarrow \frac{B}{y^2}, \quad (f, g, h, p) \rightarrow (f, g, h, p), \quad (9)$$

allows us to fix the event horizon to $r_h = 1$ in the numerical computations. The numerical solutions are validated by the constraint equations (6). Further numerical details are provided in Appendix C.

Using the standard holographic dictionary, thermodynamic quantities of the boundary theory can then be obtained from the near boundary expansion of the bulk fields (7). Here, we collect the expressions relevant to the present analysis (see [93] for a complete derivation). In terms of the coefficients appearing in the near boundary expansions (7), the energy density ϵ , the anisotropic transverse/longitudinal pressures $\mathcal{P}_{\perp/\parallel}$, and the charge density ρ are expressed as

$$\epsilon = -3f_4, \quad \mathcal{P}_{\perp} = -\frac{B^2}{4} - f_4 - 4h_4, \quad \mathcal{P}_{\parallel} = -f_4 + 8h_4, \quad \rho = -2A_{t2}. \quad (10)$$

The temperature T and entropy density s of the boundary system are determined by the surface gravity and the Bekenstein–Hawking entropy, respectively

$$T = -\frac{f'(r)}{4\pi} \Big|_{r=r_h}, \quad s = \frac{4\pi g(r)h(r)}{r^3} \Big|_{r=r_h}. \quad (11)$$

The free energy density w is given by

$$w = -\mathcal{P}_{\parallel} = -\mathcal{P}_{\perp} - M_B B = \epsilon - Ts - \mu\rho, \quad (12)$$

and the first law of thermodynamics takes the form

$$\delta w = -s\delta T - \rho\delta\mu - M_B\delta B, \quad (13)$$

where the magnetization M_B reads

$$M_B = -\left(\int_0^{r_h} \left[\frac{B}{r} \left(\frac{h}{g} - 1\right) + \frac{k}{2}(A_t A_z' - A_t' A_z)\right] dr + B \ln r_h\right). \quad (14)$$

We have verified these thermodynamic quantities extracted from our numerical calculations and confirmed that the first law (13) is satisfied within a relative error of below $< 10^{-3}$.

Figure 7. The Chebyshev coefficients c_N in the expansions of bulk fields and the violation of the constraint equation for $B = 0.338$ at $T = 10^{-2}$ (top) and $T = 10^{-5}$ (bottom). The plots are shown for $k = k_{\text{susy}} = 2/\sqrt{3}$ and $\mu = 1$.

C Numerical details

In this section, we provide details on the pseudo-spectral method [92] employed in our numerical calculations. Spectral methods typically exhibit exponential convergence with increasing grid points when the solutions are analytic. However, the presence of logarithmic terms in the boundary expansion (see (7)) for bulk fields spoils this rapid convergence. Additionally, studying the physics of the EMCS theory within the QCR necessitates working at extremely low temperatures, where the bulk fields develop prohibitively steep gradients near the horizon. Such numerical challenges typically require a substantial increase in grid points to maintain accuracy.

To overcome the numerical difficulties caused by the logarithmic terms in the boundary expansion and resolve the strong steep gradients, we introduce auxiliary fields utilizing the asymptotic behavior near the conformal boundary

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(r) &= 1 + \frac{B^2}{6} r^4 \ln r - r^4 + (1-r)r^4 \tilde{f}(r), & g(r) &= 1 - \frac{B^2}{12} r^4 \ln r + r^4 \tilde{g}(r), \\
 h(r) &= 1 + \frac{B^2}{12} r^4 \ln r + r^4 \tilde{h}(r), & p(r) &= (1-r)r^4 \tilde{p}(r), \\
 A_t(r) &= (1-r) \left(\mu + r \tilde{A}_t(r) \right), & A_z(r) &= r^2 \tilde{A}_z(r).
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

We then employ an analytical mesh refinement strategy by mapping the radial coordinate $r \in [0, 1]$ to $\xi \in [0, 1]$ via the transformation

$$r = 1 - \frac{\sinh[\lambda(1 - \xi^2)]}{\sinh \lambda}. \tag{16}$$

Here, the parameter λ can gradually increase the grid points near the horizon $r = 1$, which is chosen to be $\lambda = |\ln T| - 1/2$ in the numerics. Note that, this type of coordinate mapping is used in [87]. As a demonstration of numerical performance, Fig. 7 shows the convergence of the Chebyshev coefficients and the violation of the constraint equations (6). The Chebyshev coefficients exhibit clear exponential decay, while the violation of the constraint equations remains at high precision, confirming the good performance of our numerical method.

D Phase diagram and the universality of the $z = 3$ QCP

At zero temperature, the system is characterized by B . As this parameter varies, the near-horizon geometry undergoes distinct configurations, resulting in a field-induced QPT. The zero temperature

ground state, particularly the near-horizon geometry at and above the QCP, is revealed in [66]. Notably, the critical magnetic field is uniquely determined by the Chern-Simons coupling k , as illustrated in Fig. 8a. It should be noted that the zero temperature ground state solution becomes singular at $k = 1/2$, while for $k < 1/2$ it no longer corresponds to the zero temperature limit of a black hole [66]. Therefore, the divergence of B_c as $k \rightarrow 1/2^+$ is a physical feature of the phase diagram, rather than an unphysical divergence requiring additional renormalization. For $k > 1/2$, we find that the critical magnetic field B_c decreases monotonically as k increases. In particular, for the Chern-Simons couplings considered in this work— $k = 2/3$, $k = k_{\text{susy}} = 2/\sqrt{3}$, and $k = 3/2$ —the corresponding critical magnetic fields are $B_c \approx 1.30165$, 0.33218 , and 0.21993 , respectively.

More specifically, the phase diagram is obtained by studying the zero-temperature near-horizon geometry at the QCP. Interestingly, at $k = 1/2$, the near-horizon description supporting the quantum-critical solution breaks down, indicating that $k = 1/2$ is a special value of the Chern-Simons coupling [see Eq. (2.19) of Ref. [64], *Class. Quant. Grav.* 27 (2010) 215022]. Nevertheless, for $k > 1/2$ and sufficiently close to $1/2$, the near-horizon solution remains well defined. We find no divergence or pathology in either the bulk fields or the UV asymptotic behavior. Therefore, the divergence of B_c should not be interpreted as a UV divergence requiring an additional renormalization procedure. Rather, it indicates that the finite B_c quantum-critical solution is pushed to increasingly large magnetic fields and ceases to exist at finite B as $k \rightarrow 1/2^+$. The holographic description itself remains well defined throughout the regime $k > 1/2$.

Figure 8. Phase diagram and the quantum critical scaling function for $z = 3$ QCP. **a** The critical magnetic field B_c as a function of Chern-Simons coupling k . **b** Comparison of the quantum critical scaling function $\phi_s(x)$ for $k = k_{\text{susy}} = 2/\sqrt{3}$ and $k = 3/2$.

Note that at $k = k_{\text{susy}} = 2/\sqrt{3}$ and $k = 3/2$, the dynamical critical exponent takes the same value $z = 3$, and in both cases the singular part of the thermal entropy near the QCP follows the scaling form $s \sim T^{1/3} \phi_s(x)$ [65, 66]. By appropriately rescaling the x and the scaling function ϕ_s , we find that the quantum critical scaling functions for these two different Chern-Simons coupling fall onto a single curve, as shown in Fig. 8b. This demonstrates that the $z = 3$ QCPs in our model are universal across different values of Chern-Simons coupling k and belong to the same universality class.

Finally, we briefly comment on the ground states for $B < B_c$. Numerical results indicate that the entropy density decreases very slowly at low temperatures and appears to saturate to a finite residual value as $T \rightarrow 0$ (see the Inset in Fig. 2c). A direct test of this conclusion would require determining the zero-temperature geometries for $B < B_c$. Even though the semiclassical analysis herein suggests a nonzero residual entropy, it is expected that quantum corrections—particularly those arising from low energy gravitational fluctuations—will ultimately restore a vanishing ground-state entropy, similar to the extremal and near-extremal Reissner-Nordström black holes [94, 95]. Moreover, as mentioned in the Discussion section, allowing spatially modulated configurations within this model may provide an alternative route to ground states with vanishing entropy [87].

E Quantum phase transition at $k = 2/3$ with $z = 2$

Here, we present results for the $z = 2$ QCP, which corresponds to the Chern-Simons coupling $k = 2/3$ in the action (1). Fig. 9a displays contour plots of the entropy density s in the $T - B$ plane. The QCR appears as the orange region in Fig. 9b. The QCP itself, indicated by the red dot in Fig. 9a, is located at $B = B_c \approx 1.30165$. At the QCP, the entropy density follows the scaling form $s \propto T^{1/2}$, as shown in Fig. 9c. For comparison, Fig. 9c also includes the temperature dependence of the entropy density in the two phases—the cohesive and fractionalized phases—corresponding to the blue and

Figure 9. Entropy density s and its quantum critical behavior. **a** Density plot of s as functions of magnetic field and temperature for $k = 2/3$ and $z = 2$. The LightCyan contours represent the isentropes and increase from right to left in steps of 0.1. The magenta dot marks the position of QCP. **b** Reconstruction of the QCR by computing the regimes where the entropy density s shows a power law scaling. **c** Temperature dependence of entropy density in different phases. The inset illustrates the entropy density at extremely low temperatures in the fractionalized phase. **d** Data collapse of the entropy density near the QCP within the temperature range $8 \times 10^{-6} \leq T \leq 10^{-4}$. The plots are for $k = 2/3$ and $\mu = 1$.

purple regions in Fig. 9b. Finally, the universal scaling function of the entropy density is obtained via data collapse, as demonstrated in Fig. 9d. Following standard scaling analysis, the dynamical exponent is determined to be $z = 2d$. Since the near-horizon geometry at the QCP is governed by a three-dimensional ‘‘Schrödinger’’ spacetime, this suggests that, via holography, the effective spatial dimension of the dual system is $d = 1$. As a result, $z = 2$ for the Chern-Simons coupling $k = 2/3$. Furthermore, data collapse of the entropy density yields $1/z\nu \approx 0.507$, from which the correlation length exponent is estimated to be $\nu \approx 0.986$.

Figure 10. Specific heat. **a** Magnetic field dependence of specific heat C at different temperatures. The vertical dashed black line marks the location of QCP. The blue point marks the maximum of the specific heat. **b** Data collapse of the specific heat near the QCR. The plots are for $k = 2/3$ and $\mu = 1$.

The behavior of the specific heat density c as a function of magnetic field at various temperatures is shown in Fig. 10a. The peaks of the specific heat curves, indicated by blue dots, shift progressively toward the critical point with the decreasing of temperature. Fig. 10b demonstrates data collapse of the specific heat within the QCR, where all data fall neatly onto a universal scaling curve. Similar to the $z = 3$ case (see Fig. 3b), there is only one peak in the universal scaling function of specific heat.

Figure 11. Magnetic properties of the QPT. **a** Magnetic field dependence of magnetization M_B at different temperatures. The vertical dashed line marks the location of QCP. **b** Behavior of magnetic susceptibility χ_B as a function of magnetic field B for various temperatures. **c** The behavior of $\partial\chi_B/\partial B$ with respect to B . The plots are for $k = 2/3$ and $\mu = 1$.

Fig. 11a-b shows the behavior of magnetization and magnetic susceptibility as a function of the magnetic field at different temperatures. Both the magnetization and magnetic susceptibility vary continuously with the magnetic field across the QCP. Since the magnetic susceptibility χ_B remains positive for magnetic field above and below B_c , this indicates that both phases are paramagnetic. Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 11c, we find that the derivative of the magnetic susceptibility with respect to B becomes discontinuous at low temperatures, signaling a third order QPT. Given that this transition is of third order for $k = 2/3$, the standard scaling relations no longer apply. As a result, only z and ν can be extracted, and the full set of critical exponents cannot be determined.

Figure 12. Grüneisen ratio of the holographic quantum criticality. **a** Magnetic field dependence of the magnetic Grüneisen ratio Γ_B across the QPT. **b** Data collapse of Grüneisen ratio. The insert fig represents the temperature scaling of Γ_B at $B = B_c$. The plots are for $k = 2/3$ and $\mu = 1$.

Having investigated the thermodynamic properties of the system, we now turn to the novel MCE associated with this quantum criticality. Fig. 12a shows the behavior of the Grüneisen ratio Γ_B as a function of the magnetic field at various temperatures. As the temperature decreases, Γ_B is observed to diverge near QCP. Notably, Γ_B remains positive throughout the transition, indicating the absence of the peak-dip structure and sign change typically observed in most QPTs. Finally, Fig. 12b demonstrates the data collapse of the Grüneisen ratio. The $\Gamma_B(B - B_c)$, when plotted as a function of $x = (B - B_c)/T^{0.507}$, collapse onto the same universal curve, confirming the universal scaling behavior of the Grüneisen ratio. Moreover, along $B = B_c$ (or $x = 0$), the Grüneisen ratio exhibits the expected scaling behavior $\Gamma_B \propto T^{-1/z\nu} = T^{-0.507}$. Therefore, we find that the Grüneisen ratio continues to exhibit divergent behavior even for a third-order QPT, and its temperature dependence at the QCP provides an effective means to extract the product $z\nu$ and hence ν . Remarkably, the value of $z\nu$ obtained from Γ_B is consistent with that deduced from the data collapse of the entropy and specific heat. This agreement suggests that the universal scaling laws governing the divergence of the Grüneisen ratio extends to third order QPTs as well.

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